

Motivation and Challenges Facing Employers in Recruiting Professional Women in Building Construction Companies in Dar-Es-Salaam, Tanzania

Morin N. Nalitolela¹, Shubira L. Kalugila², Mercy B. Muganyizi³ and Dennis N.G.A.K. Tesha⁴

¹Student, Department of Building Economics, Ardhi University (ARU), TANZANIA

²Senior Lecturer, Department of Architecture, Ardhi University (ARU), TANZANIA

³Assistant Lecturer, Department of Architecture, Ardhi University (ARU), TANZANIA

⁴Assistant Lecturer, Department of Building Economics, Ardhi University (ARU), TANZANIA

⁴Corresponding Author: teshaville@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The study intended to assess the motivation and challenges facing employers in recruitment of professional women in building construction companies; by analyzing motivation; examining the challenges encountered; and proposing the possible measures to overcome challenges facing employers in recruiting professional women in building construction companies, in Dar-Es-Salaam, Tanzania. This descriptive designed survey study, engaged large size contractors as a unit of analysis, with building contractors from Class I and II, within Dar-Es-Salaam Tanzania, as a study population and a sample. Moreover, the study involved non-probability sampling; specifically, judgmental sampling, which was used in determining the number of registered building construction firms in Dar-Es-Salaam particularly from Class I and II. Literature review; open and closed ended questionnaires administered to employers and human resources managers in building construction companies in Dar-Es-Salaam, were used in collecting primary and secondary qualitative and quantitative data. In collecting data, total of 56 questionnaire were distributed, whereby only 41 (73%) were returned. Quantitative data were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), while qualitative data were analyzed thematically. Findings revealed the need to address gender balance; non-discriminatory policy; improved staff retention (you can keep your employees, boost their morale); a better reflection to the customers or clients; encourage organization to change from gender stereotype; different perspective (benefits from different points of view and approaches); enhance collaboration (improve team processed and group collaboration); the perception of women being more multitasked than men, and the need to explore a wide talent pool; women are professionally ethical, committed to their work, and less corrupt, with better listening and soft skills; improve reputation (no gender biasness to your company); and women are loyal, practical innovative, and patience, as the most prevalent motivations that; pushes employers to recruit professional women in building construction companies. Furthermore, the critical challenges revealed were; work-life balance, private life demands, emotions, and non-family friendly working hours; lack of good recruitment practises, procedures and selection plans; lack of good staff development plan; lack of gender policy; lack of confidence and low number of female applicants in the building construction

industry; and lack of proper motivation and mentorship policy. The study concluded that; more attention must be made on recruiting more women in building construction industry as a part of the gender equality, in order to increase their participation number in the construction industry, against male, alongside addressing all the challenges and motivation factors revealed in the study. Lastly, the study recommended; incentives (such as training and mentoring); support and encouragement of women participation in construction; enhancement of labour laws and regulations; and mandatory to recruitment of more women in construction industry.

Keywords-- Motivation, Challenges, Employers, Recruiting, Professional Women, Building Construction, Dar-Es-Salaam; Tanzania

I. INTRODUCTION

The construction industry apart from being the largest employer in the world, providing job opportunities to a large number of skilled and un-skilled work force; it is a key sector in any country's economic growth, and a major contributor to any country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Kumar (2013); Rajanna (2015); Haupt & Harinarain (2016); Lombardi (2017); Kikwasi & Escalante (2018). Basically, the worldwide phenomenon, and predominant image of construction industry is that; it has been and continues to be a very much leading male-dominated sector of economic, that reflects the image of masculinity, hostility, challenging and dangerous environment, with women being seriously under-represented, under-utilised and under-recognition, hence causing a major obstacle for equal women participation in the industry, ILO (2011); Ahuja & Kumari (2012); Jaafar & Othman (2013); Sospeter *et al.*, (2014); Wright (2014); Jonas (2015); Tessa (2016); Osobor (2016); Sospeter (2016); Sang & Powell (2012) in Francis (2017); Książek & Kosy (2017); Rosa *et al.*, (2017); Aneke *et al.*, (2017); Malekela & Daata (2018); Alves & English (2018); Aretoulis (2018); Aboagye-Nimo *et al.*, (2019).

Moreover, its male-domination and territoriality is reflected in the writings by Haupt & Fester (2012); Sangweni (2015); Rajanna (2015); Naismith *et al.*, (2017) which reports that; women employed and represented in construction industry in the world, are small in numbers with only between 7% and 25% of female construction workers, despite an increase on their representation in other sectors of the economy, (e.g. in the European Union). This is also reflected in CIF (2019), which exemplify that; the male-domination in the construction industry, accounts for 99% of the jobs, in United Kingdom (UK). According to Hatipkarasulu & Roff (2011); Sospeter (2016); Rosa *et al.*, (2017); Buser (2016) in Malekela & Daata (2018); this is due to the fact that; the construction industry is traditionally a male-dominated industry, which is historically described as a non-traditional occupation for women, alongside being more resistant than other economic industries, on increasing their participation.

Globally, there have been several efforts on raising the number of women participation in economic activities, in order to counter the number of women labour issues (e.g. in construction industry), with areas such as women equality and empowerment via wages and labour market representation in the Millennium Development Goals (MDG), (2000-2015), and women access to work, discrimination and wage gap in the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), (2015-2030), being looked up on. Essentially, educating, recruiting and retaining more women in the construction industry is of massive importance and the best option to deal with the under-representation as well as many other issues facing women in construction. Example, studies by Othman & Jaafar (2013) and Fernando, *et al.*, (2014) highlights onto low number of women holding managerial positions in the industry, gender divisions and vertical segregation, the requirements to attract more women to construction industry in order to fill the skills gaps, and to make changes within the industry in terms of gender segregation and enhanced productivity; but still the construction industry experiences shortage of skilled women workforce globally, hence creating an alarming necessity for a more research on the phenomena, especially on what the employers look onto, as well as challenges the face when recruiting professional women in construction, specifically in the building sector.

The necessity to introduce women in construction, is due to the fact that; construction industry is experiencing an ongoing on shortage of skilled labour, and women recruitment in the building construction workforce, has been identified as a potential solution to overcome the skills gap while enhancing equal opportunities for women within the industry, alongside bringing diversity within the construction industry. Thus, providing abled skilled labour through the employment of women on sites can facilitate

and improved rate of construction and quality of building English, Haupt & Smallwood (2006). The facilitation of “untapped resource” of women participation, could expand inclusivity and significantly improve in the current skills shortage faced by the industry, English, Haupt & Smallwood (2006). Furthermore, a study conducted in United Kingdom (UK) by Scott *et al.*, (2008) details that; inequalities in construction have proved to be very resistant when it comes to change, with women continuing to be more likely than men to reap adverse job-related penalties associated with child rearing and family care; conditions for part-time work; and work-family or work-life balance which remains to be very different for women in comparison to men.

The same women issues in construction, have also been facing the Tanzania construction industry, despite its continuation on being one of the key sectors in the economy with a growth rate of 7.9% in 2019 and 10.2% in 2010; while employing 9% of the workforce in Tanzania, still it is regarded as male dominated. Recruiting more women in the construction industry is important as it will help to retain them in the construction industry. However, today’s construction industry is convectional in employing women due to extreme gender stratification. Employers and human resource managers in building construction companies need to consider the professional women involvement in various construction works.

According URT (2010) in Ngonde (2015); URT (2016); NBS (2016); Luvara & Mwemezi (2017); NBS (2018); Kikwasi & Escalante (2018), construction industry includes real estate, transport infrastructure and other civil works, such as water supply, and has played a key role in the country’s economic growth as one of fast growing sectors, becoming a major contribution in the Country’s Gross Domestic Product (GDP) followed by trade and repair, transport and communication, and agriculture, by contributing a percentage growth rate of 7.4% of the country’s GDP in 2006; 7.8% in 2009; 8.0% in 2010; 12.5% in 2014; and 13.6% in 2015. The country’s construction sector growth rate as per NBS (2016), NBS (2018), in Kikwasi & Escalante (2018), is due to an increase on the ongoing construction and rehabilitation activities (i.e. commercial and residential buildings, and ongoing infrastructure projects such as the national roads network, bridges, hospitals, schools, water supply, electricity, Standard Gauge Railway (SGR), expansion of various regional airports, flyovers at TAZARA and Ubungo intersection in Dar-Es-Salaam, the Songosongo natural gas project, which involved the construction of a 512 Kilometers pipeline from Mtwara to Dar-Es-Salaam, and the construction of Phase 01 of the Dar-Es-Salaam Rapid Transit Bus, etc.). Thus, its growth pace against low number of women construction workers available, gender inequality and discrimination, wage unbalance etc. makes it

more interesting in studying the motives that drives the employers, as well as challenges they face when recruiting women in building construction industry.

A. Problem Statement

Construction industry, apart from being identified as a sector not suitable for women, due to the nature of most of its works being physically demanding; it is regarded as a 4D industry with a negative public image of being dull, dirty, dangerous and difficult, hence leading to a low number of women participation, Haupt & Harinarain (2016); Anuar *et al.*, (2017); Raid & Sempik (2012) in Francis (2017), Lombardi (2017). Likewise, it is considered to be tough, and conflict ridden, with long-hours work norms, as well as a strong culture of presenteeism and Human Resource Management (HRM) processes and procedures, that are both inequitable and inconsistent, Raid & Sempik (2012) in Francis (2017). Despite its hostility image toward women inclusion via recruitment; construction industry remains to be one of the increasingly growing key economic sector in the country, that needs the skills and talents of everyone, including women, Kikwasi (2005) in Kihupi (2012); Sospeter *et al.*, (2014); URT (2016); URT (2017). Lack of women in construction industry has been and continues to be a concern for many years in terms of presentation, despite women comprising half of the world's population, Kumar (2013). In fact, it continues to be a site of gender discrimination and inequality across cultures and nationalities, hence affecting women's recruitment, retention and progress, alongside being largely attributable to cultural and structural barriers, Galea *et al.*, (2015); French & Strachan (2015); Navarro-Astor *et al.*, (2017); Tessa (2016); Sang & Powell (2012) in Malekela & Daata (2018). Example in Tanzania where in the last decade, there has been a relatively high economic growth, averaging between 6% to 7% a year, as per World Bank (2018) in Kikwasi & Escalante (2018); the construction industry which is the pillar for socio-economic development, employ 9% of the workforce in Tanzania, and 57% of the gross fixed capital formation, CRB (2013) in Sospeter (2016); Luvara & Mwemezi (2017). In that contribution, less than 2% of 8,246 construction firms are owned by women, alongside women constituting only 2.4% of the construction workforce, thus evincing a large percentage of male-domination in the industry, whereby 10% of the 2.4% of women in construction workforce, work in a professional capacity, 84% are in secretarial posts and the remaining 6% work in the crafts and trades, CITB (2003); CRB (2013); NBS (2014); CRB (2015).

The under-representation and ratio of women-men in the construction industry, which has created a gender inequality, raises an issue specifically on knowing the women's recruitment motivation and challenges on the employer's side, especially due to the fact that; most of the

previous studies focused more on the challenges facing women professionals in the construction sector in general. Example, studies by Gale (1994); Amaratunga *et al.*, (2009); Kikwasi (2005); and Hakala (2008) in Sospeter *et al.*, (2014); all attempted to examine the factors that affect the low level of women's participation in the construction industry, Meza (2010) & Kihupi (2012) looked onto challenges facing female construction professional and non-professional workers working in office and on construction sites in Tanzania, while Kamugisha (2012) based on the analysis of the factors influencing the choice of careers in building industry by professional women in Tanzania. Mdemu (2012) studied the experience of female quantity surveyors working in the construction firms, while Msangi (2018) assessed the motivation and challenges facing women quantity surveyors in consulting firms, but still the number of women professionals recruited in the construction industry is still low. Nevertheless, there is no study on the employer's perspective specific for construction sector, apart from the general recruitment challenges. Thus, the study aims at assessing the motivation and challenges facing employers in recruiting professional women in building construction companies in Dar-Es-Salaam, Tanzania; by analyzing motivation influencing employers and examining challenges facing employers, in recruiting professional women in building construction companies; and proposing possible measures that can be employed in order to overcome challenges facing employers in recruiting professional women in building construction companies in Dar-Es-Salaam, Tanzania.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Construction

Construction is the process of constructing a building or infrastructure, and it is an industry which comprises 6% to 9% of the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of developed countries. It starts with planning, design and financing; then continues until the project is built and ready for use. In construction there are three sectors; i.e. buildings, infrastructure and industrial, which includes but not limited to; construction of schools, hospitals, residential houses, offices, townships, highways, roads, marine ports, airports, railways, power projects, irrigation projects. Basically, building construction is the process of adding structure to real property or construction of buildings, and its projects consist of common elements such as design, financial, estimating and legal considerations, projects of varying sizes may reach undesirable end results, such as structural collapse, cost overruns and litigation. For this reason, those with experience in the field make detailed plans and maintain careful oversight during the project to ensure a positive outcome Jimoh *et al.*, (2016). Construction can be formal or informal. It involves both

skilled and unskilled occupations like bricklaying, surveying, carpentry, concreting, demolition, dogging, painting and decorating, rigging, roof tiling, scaffolding, solid plastering, steel fixing, wall and ceiling lining, wall and floor tiling and many other sub-trade. Low paid workers: i.e. as head-loaders, carrying bricks, cement, sand and water, digging earth, mixing cement, and breaking stones, ILO (2011). With the formal construction already showing a lot of challenges and scarcity in terms of women work force, a study of informal construction workers in Dar-Es-Salaam (United Republic of Tanzania) revealed that; only 4% of the total population of workers were women, and their main roles included stone crushing, selling food to workers on construction sites and working in offices as storekeepers and cleaners, leaving very few women working in direct construction occupations, such as masonry, carpentry or electricity, ILO (2015).

B. The Construction Industry

Construction industry is one of the most key industrial sector in terms of economic growth and employment activities in the country, URT (2016); URT (2017). It is a sector that employs workers in the two main categories: managers and professionals who plan, organize, and advise on specialist functions or field activities, and direct and coordinate all activities and resources involved in construction operations; and, construction trades, who construct, install, finish, maintain and repair internal and external structures of domestic, commercial and industrial buildings and civil constructions, Gurjao (2006); Employment Service (1990) in Jonas (2015). The construction industry is unique because it affects every one's life and it is one of the few industries whose products can increase in value over time. It is often at the cutting edge of technological development, offering a wide range of challenging employment opportunities. Although the industry offers many employment opportunities, there is a critical skills shortage in the industry, especially on the women side. Entrance of young men into the industry has decreased over time and selection of a construction related professional as a career choice is not popular among young students. The shortage is also depicted in a study by Gurjao (2006) which exemplify that; the UK's construction industry is facing a skills shortage, which threatens the long term health of the industry and its all construction firms¹, due to suffering from recruitment problems. URT (2016) reports that; the growth rate of Tanzania construction sector was fast between 2010 and 2011, increasing from 10.3% to 22.9% respectively. Thereafter, it declined to 3.2% growth

rate in 2012 (mainly due to the declined investment and stalled construction activities caused by non-payment to contractors) before rising to 14.6% in 2013 and dropping slightly to 14.1% in 2014. It also recorded a growth of 4.3% in Q1 2016 compared to 23.2% in Q1 2015. The growth also recorded an increase in the registration of construction companies at an average rate of 7.2% per year, which is a growth rate of 11.1% per year for the period of five years (i.e. 2010 - 2014), Luvara & Mwemezi (2017); URT (2017); Okangi (2018).

C. The Need for Women in the Construction Industry

Basically in education, the number of women entering university has continued to increase over recent years, with women now accounting for over 50% of the student population. Despite this, women only constitute 8% of construction students. The lack of women in construction has been a concern for many years. The studies in this area have been invaluable in pinpointing the factors militating against the participation of women in the construction work place, and in particular, the recruitment into the construction professions. For one to understand the women recruitment in construction, he/she must understand their categorical groups in the industry. Ahuja & Kumari (2012); Książek & Kosy (2017) details that; women in the construction industry can be classified in three groups; i.e.

- Women working in professional or technical positions, like Architects, Engineers, Project Managers, Project Procurement, etc.
- Women in administrative positions like Finance, Human Resources, etc.; and
- Women as construction labour or workforce on-sites.

The negligible presence of women in construction industry, has attracted both government and industry players' attention with focus on studying the issues leading to less participation of women in the sector, and finding ways to resolve these issues Ahuja & Kumari (2012), with this study intending to look into their recruitment motivations and challenges in the building construction industry, specifically on the employers side. This is in line with Książek & Kosy (2017) results which reported on the women entrance into the different stages of profession in the construction industry, that can be identified as:

- Young women joining after completing their education,
- Women starting on with family responsibilities and to be retained in the workforce,
- Women trying to return or returning to work following a career break, and
- Women who may join construction industry seeking a career change.

Despite, construction industry being one of the important economic sector employing a large number of

¹ **Construction Firms**:- include consulting and contracting firms, corporation, organization, partnership or individual person that contact to conduct development project and undertake production as part of construction projects of any kind including repair and renovation, URT (2017).

people on its work force, Rajanna (2015); it still needs gender diversity to sustain development and growth, with women having a lot to contribute in terms of workforce, as it is done by the men. This is even evinced in writings by Rosa *et al.*, (2017) which reports that; a diversified workforce with gender balance always bring about higher levels of productivity. With the labor shortage, combined with the world's continuation on the need for infrastructure, housing, and other construction investment, as well as the need for women to join the industry and rise to the ranks within the construction workforce, is absolutely important, Buncio (2019). Basically, for a number of years women have been moving into professional work such as Law, Accountancy and Medicine, all of which require high level of qualifications and are considered attractive because of the perceived high level of social status. Today, numbers of women and men are almost equal in these sectors. But occupational sectors such as engineering and construction have not seen a corresponding change in the make-up of the work force EOC (2004). Given the fact that in 2017, the population of Tanzania was estimated at 52,554,628 compared to 50,941,672 people in 2016, with Dar-Es-Salaam alone hosting 10% of the national population; while women accounting for 51.4% of the distribution by sex estimated at 26,867,474, of the Tanzanian population, URT (2012) in Sospeter (2016); URT (2018); CLGF (2017), gives a clear picture on the importance of women inclusion in the construction industry, and the study conduction in Dar-Es-Salaam.

Moreover, URT (2018) reports that; women's participation in the labour market has risen to 69.2% of all women compared to men whose participation was 81.4%, alongside the demand for construction experiencing steady growth over the past five years. With this pace, clearly the industry cannot afford a skills shortage at such a time. The Equal Opportunities Commission (EOC) investigation into segregation of men and women in training and work found a strong correlation between sector specific skills shortages and the underrepresentation of women. The EOC says breaking gender barriers will help solve skill shortages. Construction, engineering, plumbing and childcare are among the most strongly gender segregated sectors of the workforce in Britain EOC (2004). The construction industry needs to find ways to balance its requirements, as an employer, if it wants to get the best out of people with child care responsibilities. The working hours culture needs to be replaced with flexible working. Better work-life balance is being demanded by both men and women as men now take part in child care responsibilities. The construction industry currently fails to address issues combining work and family commitment, treating them as separate. The construction industry is facing a 'demographic time-bomb' that is, the pool of traditional male applicants is contracting and the current workforce is ageing leading to problems of skill

shortages and recruitment. Therefore, there is a need to tap into the talents of the 'other half' of the work force; women and ethnic minorities. This appears to be the driving force to encourage women into the industry rather than equal opportunity EOC (2004).

D. Image of the Construction Industry

The construction industry is not homogeneous; it is a major component of investment with high economics growth potential, and a sector with untapped opportunities related to a wide range of construction activities, products and skills, which may either be new construction works or maintenance and repair works, that includes design, building, civil engineering, oil and gas, heavy engineering, and companies manufacturing and fabricating components and products used by the industry, ILO (2007) in Sospeter *et al.*, (2014). Its companies range from those employing over 5000 people to small and medium sized enterprises that are the backbone of the industry, which also continues to face the imbalance between women and men in terms of workforce. Fundamentally, women are not adversely affected by the loud character of the industry and do not experience significant verbal abuse, but they experience sexual harassment. This is an issue that is perceived differently by men. Compared to 56% women only 39% men perceive that women face sexual harassment. This indicates that women should be at senior positions so that issues pertaining to women can be addressed. Women perceive that they can achieve top managerial positions, but men have different perception, Ahuja & Kumari (2012). Besides, Haupt & Harinarain (2016), stated that young people need to be attracted to a career in construction by promoting the industry, whereby a positive image is needed to attract employees and investors to firms. If there is a perception that the industry is operating unethically, then it cannot attract any employees, investors or customers. However, today's construction industry is convectional in employing women due to extreme gender stratification. Most of women working in the construction industry carry out managerial, technical and specialized work while the employment of women at the professional level is very little and the data are limited to zero, but in many countries, these represents <1% of the work force Jimoh *et al.*, (2016).

E. Recruitment

Employees' recruitment is defined differently by researchers. Jovanovic (2004); Zinyemba (2014), defines it as a process of actively seeking and attracting a great pool of high quality potential job applicants in sufficient numbers, alongside selecting the best among them, to fill vacant positions within a company. According to Opath (2010), recruitment is the process of finding and attracting suitably qualified people to apply for job vacancies in the organization. Breaugh & Starke (2000); Gamage (2014),

highlights that; recruitment includes practices and activities carried out by the organization, with the primary purpose of identifying and attracting potential employees, through a systematic recruitment process which involves identifying vacancies, job analysis, job description, person qualification and advertising. On the process of recruitment, advertisement is done in order to have a greater pool of applicants from which to select. However, sourcing in the right place is a recruitment challenge for the human resources manager, recruitment efforts may be made ineffective when the advertising does not reach the intended target destination. A good recruitment and selection process ensures conformity to legal requirements as dictated by the Labour Relations Act Zinyemba (2014), whereby the process:-

- should be transparent and should ensure privacy and observance of equal opportunity legislation,
- should ensure that the selection process is fair and meets legal requirements,
- should ensure that administrative procedures are handled efficiently, and
- should help in injecting new blood to the organization.

The underrepresentation of women in construction is attributed to several structural and attitudinal barriers which may be gender-centered or organization-centered, Fernando *et al.*, (2014) and it reflects the phenomenon of “glass ceiling”, Gurjao (2006). Globally, women in construction perceives themselves that; though they may not face major discrimination, but they have to work harder during their intern, than their male colleagues, in order to prove themselves all the time, so that they may be retained or recruited English & Hay (2015).

F. Recruitment Procedures in the Construction Company

Gyasi (2012), examined the processes through which companies recruits employees, so as to ascertain whether the processes influence women’s entry into the construction industry, by including how vacancies are made known to the public for employment, who is responsible for recruitment, methods used to select applicants and how applicants are expected to submit application for employment. His study revealed that; all classes of companies advertised vacancies through friends and colleagues. Managers of the companies indicated that; friends and colleagues can bring qualified and better personnel rather than media. The method of advertisement through various media of the construction companies limits their scope of access to human resource that may enter the industry, since friends and colleagues cannot advertise to a fair extent. It also implies that people who have gained entry into the industry, continues to work in the industry whilst those outside, who may find it difficult entering the industry, since they may not be known by friends and

colleagues who recommended people for employment. In view of this, persons in charge of recruitment were also investigated,

Gyasi (2012) reveals that; the recruitment of people for employment is mostly done by Managing Directors of construction companies. In addition, heads of department like foremen were in charge of the selection of masons and labourers. Recruitment in the construction industry is mostly done by one person, either the managing directors or a head of department in company. This has the possibility of employing people who may appeal to the expectation of one person who is doing the recruitment and not the company as whole. Since the construction activities may deemed non-traditional for women, women may be at a more disadvantage.

G. Motivation

Motivation as per Barg *et al.*, (2014) refers to a set of energetic forces that originate both within as well as beyond an individual’s being, to initiate work-related behaviour and to determine its form, direction, intensity and duration. Motivation is intangible, and a hypothetical construct used to explain human behaviour. Furthermore, motivation is commonly sourced from intrinsic or extrinsic motives, where intrinsic motivation involves people doing an activity because they find it interesting, and derive spontaneous satisfaction from the activity itself, while extrinsic motivation, in contrast, requires an instrumentality between the activity and some separable consequences such as tangible or verbal rewards; hence, satisfaction comes not from the activity itself but rather from the extrinsic consequences to which the activity leads, to enhance motivation in a company. Rusetski (2011) asserts that; employers need to make an effort to understand and guide their workers in achieving the organizational goals or targets, in order to be effective in handling their project team or their subordinates. They should have an understanding of motivational forces as well as taking seriously the responsibility to create a happy work environment for the employees. More importantly, in the construction industry, the ability to build a project team, motivate others, create organizational structures and a happy work place environment to the workers. Motivational needs are required to make successful project management.

According to Gurjao (2006), construction clients are demanding industry change, in terms of different skills, traits, and maybe integrate more in women than men. They want less confrontation and more of a ‘can do’ approach. Moreover, they want to safe work site with zero accidents, and a skilled workforce that cares about the quality of the product. The need is for customer-focused customer care, people with good interpersonal, understanding, empathy, facilitation and listening skills, trust and openness. Women also possess fine motor skills and attention to detail. The

industry has to radically change how it does business, finding the right balance between masculine and feminine traits. Thus, having more women can add value in the construction industry. The industry may have to recognize and build upon the strengths and characteristics of women; this does not necessarily mean it has to change. Women are needed at all levels, in management, in design, in trade skills and in all the various parts of the supply chain Gurjao (2006).

H. Gender

Gender refers to the roles and responsibilities of men and women that are created in our societies, families and our cultures. The concept of gender also includes the expectations held about the characteristics, attitudes and likely behaviours of both women and men. Gender roles and expectations are learned. They can change overtime and they vary within and between cultures, systems of social differentiation such as political status, class, ethnicity, physical and mental disability, age and more, modify gender roles. The concept of gender is vital because, when applied to social analysis, it reveals how women's subordination (or men's domination) is social constructed. As such, the subordination can be changed or ended UNESCO (2003).

The construction industry remains largely dominated by male and able-bodied personnel, despite a range of initiatives over the last 20 years that have sought to challenge this profile. In the United Kingdom (U.K.), women make up approximately 10% of employees in construction, compared to 46% across all industries ONS (2009). In higher education the figures are slightly better, with women representing 18% of Civil Engineering students and 31% of Architecture, Building and Planning students HESA (2009). Evidence demonstrates that the persistent of gender inequality in construction affects women's recruitment, retention and progress and is largely attributable to cultural and structural barriers Sang & Powell (2012). Dainty *et al.*, (2000) argues that; women are focused in office based and administrative support roles within the construction industry, largely because of gender stereotypes beliefs of managers. Lack of access to skill development opportunities, such as working on site, limit women's career development within the sector. Status of gender in Tanzania construction sectors views the ratio of females and males in the industry. Also, views trend of presentation in the years in order to get the picture of future position for women in construction industry. The status of gender can view several parameters in the industry, i.e. graduates into the construction programme, ratio of gender in the professional registration and the ratio in the recruitment in the construction firms Msangi (2018).

I. Statistics of Women in Management and Professional Position in the Construction Companies

The man power in the Tanzania construction sector is far below than expected. An extract from various regulatory bodies, as seen Table #2.01 indicates that; the number of registered professionals and technicians is still low compared to potential employers. This supports the findings of Lema (2017) which depicted that; there is a significant gap in the skill demand-supply in Tanzania.

Table #2.01; Comparison of registered professionals, technicians and potential employers both males and females

SN.	Potential Employees		Potential Employers	
	Specialization	Number	Organization	Number
01.	Consulting Engineer	531	Contractors	8,814
02.	Professional Engineer	6,657	LGAs	133
03.	Quantity Surveyor	439	Consulting Firms	674
04.	Architects	466	CGAs & Agencies	29
05.	Technicians	727	Private Employers	Various

Source: Kikwasi & Escalante (2018), modified by Author (2020).

The lack of women in construction has been a concern for many years. The studies in these areas have been invaluable in pinpointing the factors militating against the participation of women in the construction work place, and in particular, the recruitment into the construction professions Agapiou (2002). Although women comprise 51.4% of the Tanzanian population URT (2012), they continue to be underrepresented, and marginalized than men on participating in primary sectors such as the construction industry. Women are marginalized due to social and cultural structures. However, the social structures and cultural systems that reinforce the continued subordination and marginalization of women have a major impact on motives for their involvement in business and perception of success, Nchimbi & Chijoriga (2009) in Sospeter (2017).

According to Dainty *et al.*, (2006) women underrepresentation in management position in all classes of construction companies results in limiting women entry into the industry. Moreover, the under-representation of women in managerial positions in the construction industry discourages new female entrants into the construction industry, with the fore knowledge that they will never move past middle management positions. In addition, the absence of role models to boost the morale of young girls to choose an occupation in the construction industry also discourages girls in choosing a career in construction. Women being in managerial position are an indication that women can progress to top positions in the construction industry. Women's presence at the managerial positions is one of the surest means of ensuring the participation in the construction industry in decision making in the construction industry. The underrepresentation of women in the industry

makes the working environment of the industry masculine hence deterring women from entering the industry, and as the result; the construction industry; the community; and the clients keeps on suffering the consequence of utilizing the potentials of one gender Dainty *et al.*, (2006).

J. Representation of Women in Construction Industry in Tanzania

According to Labour Force Survey of 2014 conducted by NBS (2014), construction industry contributes 2.1% of the total labour force in Tanzania. The female’s labour force in the construction industry was 0.1% whereas the figure for males was 4.0% of the total labour force, Table #2.02. Comparing 0.1% for females and 4.0% for males, this implies that the females employed in the construction sector is only 2.4% whereas males were 97.6% of the construction industry labour force. This situation is not different from the other countries.

Table #2.02; the employment by sector and gender in percentage in 2014

SN.	SECTOR	MALE	FEMALE	ALL
01.	Agriculture, Forestry & Fishing,	64.0	69.9	66.9
02.	Mining & Quarrying,	1.7	0.4	1.1
03.	Manufacturing	3.6	2.6	3.1
04.	Construction	4.0	0.1	2.1
05.	Wholesale & Trade	12.4	12.8	12.7
06.	Transport & Storage	5.0	0.2	2.6
07.	Accommodation & Food Service	1.4	6.5	3.9
08.	Administrative & Support Service	1.0	0.3	0.6
09.	Education	2.1	2.1	2.1
10.	Health and Social Work Activities	0.7	1.0	0.8
11.	Others	4.1	4.1	4.1
	TOTAL	100.0	100.0	100.0

Source: NBS (2014).

Malekela & Daata (2018) reports that; recruitment in Tanzania construction industry has been shown to be discriminatory. This is evident on the number of male employees compared to females from site to administrative level. Culture and environment have also been major factors limiting women in the industry, despite the representation and percentage (%) of women in a building construction industry increasing compared to years back.

Table #2.03; the representation of women professional staffs by gender in building construction companies with Class I and II, in Tanzania

SN.	Construction Companies	Gender		Percentage of Responses (%)
		Female	Male	
01.	Class One (I)	53	202	26.3%
02.	Class Two (II)	19	78	24.4%
	TOTAL	72	280	25.7%

K. Motivation of Employers in the Construction Industry

According to Whiteley (2002), motivation is having the encouragement to do something and it

determines why, whether and how we work. Successful managers require sophisticated and organizational skills, as well as the effectiveness to manage the multidisciplinary activities that approve of the ability to understand the organizational and behavioural elements, in order to create work environment that suits the team’s motivational needs.

Table #2.04: the motivations of employers in recruitment of professional women in construction industry

SN.	MOTIVATIONS	AUTHORS
01.	Women are loyal, patience, innovative, and professionally ethical	Watts (2009); Othman & Jaafar (2013); Malekela & Daata, (2018)
02.	Committed to their work, and less corrupt	Malekela & Daata(2018)
03.	Better listening skills and soft skills	English & Hay (2015)
04.	Women’s ability to work with people, confidence, adaptability, dedication, focus, integrity, leadership skills, ability to bring teams together, networking, etc.	Fernando <i>et al.</i> , (2014);
05.	Image of the industry,	Fielden <i>et al.</i> , (2000)
06.	To promote a ‘can do’ attitude among women,	CIB (2003)
07.	Encourage organization to change from gender stereotype,	Hesa (2009)
08.	Different perspective (having both men and women)	ILO (2018)
09.	Enhance collaboration (improve team processed and group collaboration)	Gyasi (2012)
10.	Improved staff retention (you can keep your employees, boost their morale to work)	Opath (2010)
11.	The need to address gender balance	Sang & Powell (2012)
12.	The need to explore a wider talent pool	Zinyemba (2014)
13.	A better reflection of your customers or clients.	Hesa (2009)
14.	Improve reputation (no gender biasness)	English & Hay (2015)
15.	Women-friendly construction sites	Haupt & Fester (2012)

P. Challenges Facing Employers in Recruitment of Professional Women in the Building Construction Companies

Recruitment should be regarded as the first step in filling a vacancy, and ideally it should be taken as a proactive process of ensuring that, the organization has the requisite skills and experience which cannot be easily built from within but sourced from outside the organization.

Table #2.05: the challenges that employers or human resources manager face on the recruitment of professional women in construction industry

SN.	CHALLENGES	AUTHORS
01.	Conflict of interest leading to nepotism (due to friendship and relationship),	Zinyemba (2014)
02.	Lack of proper motivation policy,	Shadare <i>et al.</i> , (2009)
03.	Lack of proper and effective selection criteria,	Samwel (2018)
04.	Lack of good recruitment and selection plans,	Samwel (2018)

05.	Lack of adequate qualified female applicants,	Kikwasi (2005)
06.	Lack of gender policy,	Sang & Powell, (2012)
07.	Physical incapability; need for workers with muscular strength,	Fernando <i>et al.</i> , (2014) Malekela & Daata(2018)
08.	Negative perception of females capabilities from other company staff,	Construction Industry Training Board,(2003)
09.	Work life balance,	CIB, (2003)
10	Less participation of women in construction sector,	Ahuja & Kumari (2012)
11.	Unsocioable work-hours and exposure to hazards, as well as unattractive image of the industry to women.	Malekela & Daata(2018)

Basically, the challenges reported in Table #2.05 were the general recruitment challenges, and are not specific to the construction industry, due to existence of very little study on the challenges facing employers in the building construction industry.

II. METHODOLOGY

In line with the research guidelines highlighted by Pruzan (2016); Kumar (2011); Kombo & Tromp (2014); Saris & Gallhofer (2014); Magigi (2016); Kothari (2019) writings; the research design employed in this empirical investigation was a descriptive designed survey study. The study assessed various large size building contractors employers and human resource managers from Class I and II, within Dar-Es-Salaam Tanzania, who were also the unit of analysis. Furthermore, the study used both qualitative and quantitative approach, which made it easier in determining the intended objectives, samples and design of the study, as well as ranking the motivation and challenges facing employers in recruitment of professional women in building construction companies.

A. Data Collection Methods

Generally, both primary and secondary data collection, were done using multiple sources of evidence. Questionnaire survey and was used to collect primary data from a portion of population of registered local large size building contractors from Class I and II, in Dar-Es-Salaam, Tanzania. The respondents answered the questions on their own, Jongo *et al.*, (2019). Some of the questions were close ended and others were open ended for the respondent to attest their own opinion, and give more information. Furthermore, secondary data concerning the motivation and challenges facing employers in recruitment of professional women in building construction companies, were collected from literature review peer reviewed journals, newsletters, magazine papers, webpages. All respondents had different years of experience as employers in the building construction industry

B. The Study Sample Size and Population

The study employed non-probability sampling techniques; specifically judgmental sampling, which was used in determining the number of registered local large size building construction firms in Dar-Es-Salaam particularly from Class I and II as sample units and sampling frame, in line with guidelines stipulated by Pruzan (2016); Kumar (2011); Kombo & Tromp (2014); Saris & Gallhofer (2014); Magigi (2016); Kothari (2019). An accessible total population of 125 employers from Class I and Class II, located in Dar-Es-Salaam, as per CRB (2019), were selected as seen in Table #3.01.

Table #3.01; the number of registered local large Building Construction Companies with Class I and II

SN.	Building Construction Companies	Registered in Tanzania	Registered & Located in Dar-Es-Salaam
01.	Class One (I)	125	95
02.	Class Two(II)	46	30
	TOTAL	171	125

Source: CRB (2020).

Basically, Dar-Es-Salaam was selected as the study area as most of the building contractors are located in the area as seen in Table #3.02. The respondents were randomly selected so that each unit of the population has identical chances of being selected, and three criteria employed in determining the appropriate size were also used. These included the level of precision, the level of confidence or risk and the degree of variability in the attributes being measured (Miaoulis *et al.*, 1976 in PEO6, 2003). Moreover, a simplified formula by Yamane (1967) in Jongo *et al.*, (2018) was used to calculate Sample Size(n), as seen below;-

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where;- *N* = Total Population Size i.e. = 125

n = The Sample Size

e = Level of Precision i.e. = 10%, and a confidence level assumed 90%

Using the study population of Small and Medium Size Building Contractors(SMSBCs) as seen in Table #3.01, the total distributed samples (N) was 56 as shown in Table #3.02.

Table #3.02: the study sample distribution of the registered local large Building Construction Companies with Class I and II

Population Type		Population Size (N) in Dar-Es-Salaam	Distributed Sample (n)
Contractors	Class I	95	25
	Class II	30	31
Total Registered Firms		125	56

Source: CRB (2020).

C. Questionnaire Design

Based on writings by Pruzan (2016); Kumar (2011); Kombo & Tromp (2014); Saris & Gallhofer (2014); Nayak & Singh (2015); Magigi (2016); Kothari (2019); the study questionnaires were prepared in accordance with objectives of the research. It was divided in three (03) parts which covered registered local large Building Construction Companies with Class I and II in Dar-Es-Salaam, Tanzania. The first part, requested on general information about respondent; the second part was divided into two main questions which covered, motivation and challenges facing employers in recruitment of professional women in building construction companies; and the fourth part, dealt with proposing possible measures to overcome challenges facing employers in recruiting professional women in building construction companies, in Dar-Es-Salaam, Tanzania. Through a quantitative approach, data used were acquired with a questionnaire survey, in which the closed and open-ended questionnaire was compiled based on the refined list above, after a pilot study.

The pilot study was carried out to mark better the quality of the questionnaire and improve reliability of the questions. Based on the 5-point Likert scale, as per Kothari (2019); the respondents (registered as building contractors from Class I and II) were asked to respond to each statements, by indicating which statement is Not Applicable, (NA) = 1; Slightly Applicable, (SA) = 2; Applicable, (A) = 3; Moderately Applicable, (MA) = 4; and Highly Applicable, (HA) = 5, so as to analyze motivation; examine the challenges encountered; and proposing the possible measures to overcome challenges facing employers in recruiting professional women in building construction companies, in Dar-Es-Salaam, Tanzania. A total number of 56 questionnaires were distributed, whereby only 41 completely filled questionnaires were returned as seen Table #3.03., equivalent to an average of 73.2% respondents, which was in line with the work of Mugenda (2003) in Mikapagaro *et al.*, (2018) that; a rate of 50% or higher is satisfactory for data analysis.

Table #3.03: the response rate to questionnaires distributed to registered Building Construction Companies with Class I and II

SN.	Respondents	Questionnaires		Percentage of Responses (%)
		Distributed	Responded	
01.	Class One (I)	30	23	76.7%
02.	Class Two (II)	26	18	69.2%
	TOTAL	56	41	73.2%

IV. RESULTS, ANALYSIS & DISCUSSION

The collected qualitative and quantitative data obtained from open-ended and close-ended respectively, processed and analyzed, whereby qualitative data were

examined and analyzed manually, through contents analysis, and categorized according to the way they relate to the research objectives and questions. Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, and computed by using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS). Mean score comparison tables were used to rank the results in order of their significance, by taking into account the mean scores as shown Table #4.01, in line with Holt (2014) & Chileshe *et al.*, (2014) writings that; simple approach using means of variables is valid. Basically, the motivations and challenges with high means score values, were determined as the most applicable to the respondents.

Table #4.01: Mean score values (M) comparison table

SN.	Mean Score (M)	Ranking	Colour
01.	3.5 ≤ M ≤ 5.0	High (Common) (Most Common Challenges and Motivations).	Yellow
02.	2.0 ≤ M ≤ 3.5	Medium (Average) (Moderate Occurring Challenges and Motivations)	Green
03.	1.0 ≤ M ≤ 2.0	Low (Unsatisfied) (Low Common Challenges and Motivations).	Red

A. Motivation Influencing Employers in Recruitment of Professional Women in Building Construction Companies

The study analyzed the motivation influencing employers in recruiting professional women in building construction companies in Dar-Es-Salaam, Tanzania; as summarized in Table #4.02,

Table #4.02: the motivation influencing employers in recruitment of professional women in building construction companies

SN.	MOTIVATIONS	T N R	Mean Score (M.S.)	SD	R A N K
01.	Women are loyal, practical innovative, and patience,	41	3.51	4.32	12
02.	Image of the industry,	41	3.44	5.59	13
03.	Women are professionally ethical, committed to their work, and less corrupt, with better listening and soft skills,	41	3.80	5.54	9
04.	The need to address non-discrimination policy,	41	4.22	7.38	2
05.	The need to address gender balance,	41	4.33	7.29	1
06.	To promote a “can do” attitude among women,	41	3.77	5.66	10
07.	The perception of women being more multitasked than men, and the need to explore a wide talent pool,	41	3.88	6.46	8
08.	Different perspective (benefits from different points of view & approaches),	41	3.97	5.76	6

09.	Encourage organization to change from gender stereotype.	41	4.19	4.82	5
10.	Enhance collaboration (improve team processed and group collaboration)	41	3.97	4.80	7
11.	Improved staff retention (you can keep your employees, boost their morale)	41	4.22	6.76	3
12.	A better reflection to the customers or clients	41	4.22	6.61	4
13.	Improve reputation (no gender biasness to your company)	41	3.63	4.82	11

The Need to Address Gender Balance;- was ranked first as the most influencing motivation, with the mean score of 4.33, and a standard deviation of 7.29, due to its importance, given employers need on balancing the gender of professional employees working in their companies, keeping on rising day to day. This is due to the fact that; gender balance can be promoted through increasing the number of professional women in building construction industries, since most of the building construction companies seem to be male-dominated. On the other hand, Loosemore *et al.*, (2003) and Sang & Powell (2012) asserts that; fair treatment of all employees should be the cornerstone of good employment practice within the construction industry, in order to deal with the persistence of gender inequality in construction which affects women’s recruitment, retention and progress, hence breaking the cultural and structural barriers.

Need to Address a Non-discrimination Policy;- was ranked second with the mean score of 4.22, and a standard deviation of 7.38, thus underlining its influence, in order to counter writing by ILO (2011); Alves & English (2018) which portrays a negative image that; women are discriminated against in all walks of life. The need also will create a barrier to women in construction against being victim of exploitation and gender discrimination, sexual harassment, intimidation, bullying for work allocation and wage distribution, (i.e. lack of pay equality or salary increase), race, color, religion, sex, national origin, age, disability and genetic information. ILO (2011); Moir *et al.*, (2011); Haupt & Fester (2012); Wright (2014); Mathew (2014); Rajanna (2015); Osubor (2016); Navarro-Astor *et al.*, (2017); Lombardi (2017); Naismith *et al.*, (2017); Aneke *et al.*, (2017); Kumar & Chaturvedi (2018); Regis *et al.*, (2019); Aboagye-Nimo *et al.*, (2019). Moreover, more women, than men, expressed concerns on various types of harassment and discriminatory work practices at their workplaces, which either affect, or reflect, their career advancement such as discriminatory work practices, Bowen *et al.*, (2011) in Francis (2017). Kumar (2013) exemplifies that; in India, women are often employed in the lower paying jobs, and other than wages, discrimination against women workers is also found at the level of recruitment, selection for skilled jobs on wage or salary and promotions.

Furthermore, Jaafar & Othman (2013) exemplify by reporting that; in Malaysia, contractors discriminate against women, based on the assumption that women go on maternity leave, making them unreliable and thus presenting a greater possibility of conflicts because of their family responsibilities. Globally women in construction perceive that though they may not face major discrimination, but they have to work harder than their male colleagues and have to prove themselves all the time English & Hay (2015). With Meza (2010), discovery on the challenges facing women professionals in the construction industry, and Kamugisha (2012), on the factors influencing the choice of careers in building industry by professional women in Tanzania, revealing that; women were still under-represented and with discrimination in their construction workplaces, hence impacted negatively on their career choices than men, it is important for employers and human resource managers on recruitment of professional women in building construction companies to address a non-discriminatory policy. The underrepresentation of women at senior levels is attributed to several structural and attitudinal barriers which may be gender-centred or organizational-centred and reflects the phenomenon of “glass ceiling”, Fernando *et al.*, (2014).

Improved Staff Retention;- was ranked third with the mean score of 4.22, and a standard deviation of 6.76, as it assists on to keep company’s employees and boost their morale to work. However, the retention of professional staff within the construction companies, must be seen as a strategic priority if building construction companies are to remain competitive in the future. A study by Nguyen (2007), revealed that; there is high turnover in the construction industry due to improper treatment of technical staff and the adopted strategies for retention.

A Better Reflection of your Customers;- was ranked fourth with the mean score of 4.22, and a standard deviation of 6.61. It is important for the employers and human resource managers to build a better reflection to their customers, so that the company can be in a better position to address customer’s needs, alongside having both men and women, due to the fact that; the building construction industry serves both men and women. Basically, women are described as employees having good communication skills, who adds to the dynamics of leadership, Fernando *et al.*, (2014); ILO (2016); Alves & English (2018).

Need to Encourage Organization to Change from Gender Stereotype²;- was ranked fifth with the mean score of 4.19, and a standard deviation of 4.82, due to being

²**Gender Stereotypes;-** “the structured group of beliefs concerning characteristics – traits, behaviour, attitudes, values and norms – that are generally thought to be typical or desirable in women or in men”, Jato (2007) in Navarro-Astor *et al.*, (2017).

considered as one of the direct antecedents of discrimination at work as per Mathew (2014) & Sangweni (2015), affecting the performance of women in construction, due its prevailing masculine attitudes and discriminatory work practices in terms of sexual harassment Bowen *et al.*, (2011); Sang & Powell (2012); Worrall (2012), in Francis, (2017); and Mdolo (2014) in Msangi (2018). Men are reluctant to accept the different perspectives women bring in the industry Worrall *et al.*, (2008), due to pervading idea that women do not have the physical qualities necessary to work adequately on building sites, because they lack physical strength or fear working at heights. For the employers and human resource managers in building construction companies it is important to encourage an organization to change from gender stereotype, by recruiting both females and males, Aneke *et al.*, (2017).

Different Perspective (Benefits from Different Points of View and Approaches);- was ranked sixth with the mean score of 3.97, and a standard deviation of 5.76, due to the fact that; hiring women, usually occurs in the final stages of the construction project, during the period of grouting, finishing and cleaning, hence creating sexual division of labor, Regis *et al.*, (2019). Thus, in-line with writing by Buncio (2019) encouraging women to enter the construction industry has many positive effects. Not only will construction start reaping the rewards of closing the labor gap, but a diverse workforce presents a myriad of benefits for companies.

Enhance Collaboration (Improve Team Processed and Group Collaboration);- was ranked seventh with the mean score of 3.97, and a standard deviation of 4.80, as good integration of workers and training enhance collaboration, alongside providing numerous sizes of equipment and uniforms Regis *et al.*, (2019).

The Perception of Women Being more Multitasked than Men, and the need to Explore a Wide Talent Pool;- was ranked eighth with the mean score of 3.88, and a standard deviation of 6.46, because women are able to perform multiple roles (i.e. multi-tasking) alongside being good relationship building, hence their recruitment is likely to hugely benefit the construction industry by bringing in different perspective, Navarro-Astor *et al.*, (2017); Pulsinelli (2011) in Aneke *et al.*, (2017). According to Watts (2009); Fortune (2010); Othman & Jaafar (2013); English & Hay (2015); Książek & Kosy (2017); Women have inherent strengths that can positively contribute to the construction industry, as they are;-

- perceived to have better listening skills and soft skills,
- perceived to be more creative than men; due to paying more; attention to detail; being more thorough, more organized and more precise, as well as being able to make a deeper and more thorough analysis,

- better at negotiating relationships and keeping peace, while men tend to be more aggressive,
- are considered to have traits like teamwork, politeness and being multi-tasking,
- stronger in communication, and empathy, compared to men hence they are able to response better to stress,
- more likely to be innovative, flexible and they can easily adopt into a participatory mode of working, and

Women are Professionally Ethical, Committed to their Work, and Less Corrupt, with Better Listening and Soft Skills;- was ranked ninth with the mean score of 3.80, and a standard deviation of 5.54. Basically studies by Fernando *et al.*, (2014); Navarro-Astor *et al.*, (2017); Rosa *et al.*, (2017); and Mdolo (2014) in Msangi (2018), revealed that; in contrast to men's careers, women comprehend and perform well more than men, as they are heterogeneous, with ability to work with people, hence progressing in a different manner, alongside having dedication, adaptability, leadership, and integrity or honesty quality, which positively influence their women's career success. This attribute can be proved by contractors with experience in working with female workers, who acknowledged their performance and competence. Previous studies as per Malekela & Daata (2018) shows a marked positive change, with major impact on economy development in countries, which has given women an opportunity, whereby countries with high female labour participation are the most successful. Moreover, women are strict to professional ethics, more committed to their work and less corrupt compared to men, Malekela & Daata (2018).

To Promote a "can do" Attitude among Women;- was ranked tenth with the mean score of 3.77, and a standard deviation of 5.66, against the notion that construction industry is a "male only image" industry, associated with the need of physical strength, adjustments to harsh outdoor working conditions and oppressive dialects, Anuar *et al.*, (2017); Aboagye-Nimo *et al.*, (2019). The argument is in-line with a claim by women in writings by Osabor (2016) & Alves & English (2018) that; what a man can do, a woman can do even better, what is needed is just to create a better women working environment, rather than hostile environment and negative attitudes.

Improve Reputation (No Gender Biasness to your Company);- was ranked tenth with the mean score of 3.63, and a standard deviation of 4.82. Jaafar & Othman (2013); CIF (2019); and Regis *et al.*, (2019) notes that; hiring new employees must not be biased by gender, due to women leaving the building construction industry, as the result of company's biasness against their gender, as well as the industry's culture. This is due to the fact that; female managers are subjected to negative stereotypes and bias, with the latter influences hiring decisions, Aretoulis (2018).

Women are Loyal, Practical, Innovative and Patience;- was ranked tenth with the mean score of 3.51,

and a standard deviation of 4.82. Apart from women being more focused, practical, and determined in whatever they do, their creativity and talents are an invaluable resource, Kikwasi (2005); Jaafar & Othman (2013); Hodginkson (2006) in Sospeter *et al.*, (2014). Moreover, Jaafar & Othman (2013) stresses that; men are more physically fit than women, but women have more capabilities in planning, organizing, and handling paperwork.

B. Challenges Facing Employers in Recruitment of Professional Women in Building Construction Companies

The study examined the challenges encountered by employers in recruiting professional women in building construction companies in Dar-Es-Salaam, Tanzania; as summarized in Table #4.03,

Table #4.03: the challenges facing employers in recruitment of professional women in building construction companies

SN.	MOTIVATIONS	T N R	Mean Score (M.S.)	SD	R A N K
01.	Conflict of interest leading to nepotism,	41	3.49	4.41	8
02.	Lack of proper motivation and mentorship policy,	41	3.51	4.33	6
03.	Lack of effective selection criteria,	41	3.39	5.11	10
04.	Lack of good staff development plan	41	3.80	5.54	3
05.	Lack of confidence and low number of female applicants in the building construction industry,	41	3.71	5.72	5
06.	Lack of gender policy,	41	3.71	6.81	4
07.	Company requirements for workers with muscular strength,	41	3.49	5.84	7
08.	Physical incapability; negative perception of female capabilities from other company staff,	41	3.39	3.82	11
09.	Work-life balance, private life demands, emotions, and non-family friendly working hours,	41	3.88	6.52	1
10.	Less participation of women,	41	3.41	3.12	9
11.	Lack of good recruitment practises, procedures and selection plans,	41	3.76	7.01	2
12.	Image of the industry,	41	3.20	4.63	12

Work-life Balance, Private Life Demands, Emotions and Non-Family Friendly Working Hours;- was ranked first with the mean score of 3.88, and a standard deviation of 6.52 in-line with studies by Mdemu (2012); Jaafar & Othman (2013); Anuar *et al.*, (2017); Navarro-Astor, *et al.*, (2017); Regis *et al.*, (2019); which revealed that; without any doubt, women (especially married women) are overloaded due to carrying out more responsibilities(i.e. domestic activities such as child-care,) and commitments in most households, which eventually creates an interference (i.e. multiple role conflict) by

making it harder for them to balance between private life demands and family commitment, thus requiring long leaves for long rest and frequent check-ups during their pregnancy, maternity leave, and family care or schedules, alongside their hiring being perceived to be costly. The difficult on balancing work and life responsibilities; long unsociable, inflexible and non-family friendly working hours especially as the project approaches the end against tight contract deadlines; negative perception on women capabilities; lack of child care facility; long and irregular work schedule; were also revealed in-line with the reports by Gyasi, (2012); Rajanna (2015); Anuar *et al.*, (2017); Lombardi (2017); Rosa *et al.*, (2017); Francis (2017); Mdolo (2014) in Msangi (2018); Kumar & Chaturvedi (2018), as challenges on recruiting women into the building construction industry. Moreover, women’s emotion act as the barrier in recruitment, due to difficult in controlling them during decision making and internship, hence hindering their attempt in progressing and being retained in the building construction industry. Certainly, controlling emotion at workplace is a skill that is quite hard to grasp and utilize especially for women, Anuar *et al.*, (2017). Furthermore, the building construction workplace is well known for involving travels to geographically diverse locations, long work hours, and high stress levels, Dainty & Lingard (2006) in Jaafar & Othman (2013). Thus, some of the employers tend to be in favor of men than women because; men are more willing to work longer hours, take financial risks and can frequently re-locate to remote building construction works, for those working on-site Sangweni (2015).

Lack of Good Recruitment Practices, Procedures and Selection Plans;- was ranked second with the mean score of 3.76, and a standard deviation of 7.01, caused by the lack of formal development procedures, lack of recognition, lack of recruitment and selection plans, poor human resource planning, and lack of even appropriation of women contributions, in-line with findings by Navarro-Astor *et al.*, (2017); Samwel (2018), which can guide their recruitment and selection process, instead of recruitment and selection process being carried anyhow and at any time, hence leading to employ a huge number of male professional, in construction industry.

Lack of Good Staff Development Plans;- was ranked third with the mean score of 3.80, and a standard deviation of 5.54, by the employers and human resource managers in building construction companies, as it impacts negatively the staffs’ development of knowledge and skills, hence ending up affecting their salary, hierarchical position, and career advancement. An effective staff development plan is one of the key factors which attracts and retain staff in a company. This is a challenge in recruitment and retaining of experienced staffs in building construction companies. Shadare *et al.*, (2019) stresses that; employee

motivation is one of the policies of managers to increase effective job management among employees in organizations.

Lack of Gender Policy;- was ranked fourth with the mean score of 3.71, and a standard deviation of 6.81, with most construction companies lacking clear gender equality, and gender policy or strategy or targets which must always be promoted, in-line with Sangweni (2015); CIF (2019); Regis *et al.*, (2019) findings. When it comes to availability of gender policy in a company, the construction industry is an extreme, due to its structure allowing greater discrimination, both direct and indirect, Książek & Kosy (2017). However, the construction industry remains largely male and able-bodied, despite a range of initiatives over the last 20 years. In United Kingdom (U.K.), women make up approximately 10% of employees in construction, compared to 46% across all industries, ONS (2009). In higher education the figures are slightly better, with women representing 18% of civil engineering students and 31% of architecture, building and planning students HESA (2009). Evidence demonstrates that; the persistence of gender inequality in building construction affects women's recruitment, retention and progress and is largely attributed to culture and structural barriers Sang & Powell (2012).

Lack of Confidence and Low Number of Female Applicants in the Building Construction Industry;- was ranked fifth with the mean score of 3.71, and a standard deviation of 5.72. This is due to low number of female applicants in the job market, caused by lack of confidence, lack of role models, Lincoln (2010) in Sospeter *et al.*, (2014). Gyasi (2012), details that; females are fewer than males in construction, training institutions and colleges because courses available at the colleges which provide entry to construction discipline require background to mathematics, science and technical drawings as qualifications, which girls and women are not attracted to study, hence reducing the number of female applicants for the construction professional jobs. In a study of 550 Australian female architects, Whitman (2005) in Francis (2017), found that women perceived both their lack of confidence and questioning their own abilities as a barrier to advancement.

Lack of Proper Motivation and Mentorship Policy;- was ranked fifth with the mean score of 3.51, and a standard deviation of 4.33, indicating that; most building construction companies lack supportive motivation policy that governs their employees' motivation practice and as a result, many employees feel unmotivated and leave the company. The result are in-line with findings by Gyasi (2012); Haupt & Fester (2012); Alves & English (2018) which revealed; lack of motivation to women such as; mentoring programmes, promotion and salary or wage rise, casual and annual leave entitlement, low remuneration, tight schedule of construction jobs and fierce competition

from their male counterparts; lack of recognition and encouragement from supervisors; as a major challenges on employers during recruitment, in most country's construction industries. Kalimullah *et al.*, (2010), advocated that; motivated employees have goals aligned with those of the organization and they direct their efforts in that direction. Moreover, the study revealed lack of mentorship policy in most construction companies, in-line with findings by Rosa *et al.*, (2017); Alves & English (2018) which revealed the absence of positive influences such as lack of role models or mentors as major obstacles in women recruitment. Mentoring is the process of building a relationship in which a more experienced mentor can assist in sharing knowledge and skills as well as assisting the development of a less experienced mentee. NWLC (2014); Guerrero *et al.*, (2016) in Francis (2017) details that; the availability of networks and mentoring in any building construction company are beneficial to employees careers, and the company at large, because mentorship that can enhance women's ability on accessing and penetrating the dominant male social networks mentorship.

V. CONCLUSION & RECOMMENDATIONS

A. Conclusion and the Study Implications

Basing on the specific objectives, the study concluded that; rather than having them working on marginal roles, more attention and proper note in terms of number against male and the potential role of women in building construction labour market, must be made when recruiting them, in order to increase their participation, so as to guarantee equal rights and opportunities to both the genders. Furthermore, women's career development in building construction continues to faces different challenges, despite being engaged in several roles in the building construction (i.e. site and office) e.g. as civil engineers in structural; clerk of works; quantity surveyors; architects; service (i.e. electro-mechanical) engineers; project managers; building materials suppliers; tradesmen in repair and maintenance etc. but their number is still low. Thus, allowing women equal opportunities in the building construction industry as men, has the potential to enhance effective socio-economic development, as long as the challenges encountered and motivations revealed during recruitment are enhanced. Moreover, the implementation of policies that address gender equality plays a major role in enhancing rate of economic growth and their ability to sustain socio-economic development. Basically, gender diversity is vital in redressing the issues of unequal opportunities within the building construction sector. Thus, the study will assist on solving issues related on the recruitment, sexism, discrimination and low number of professional women in the building construction industry by providing suggestions on how to deal with the

challenges and motivations related with women recruitment. It will facilitate the development as well as growth and advancement of women, hence changing the male dominated building construction industry into more gender friendly, equitable and inclusive building construction industry. Furthermore, it will provide a better understanding of how to attract, recruit, increase and retain professional women within the building construction industry and ensure gender diversity.

B. Recommendations

Basing on the findings and conclusion drawn, the study recommends the following measures to overcome challenges facing employers in recruiting professional women in building construction companies, in Dar-Es-Salaam, Tanzania.

- **Incentives (such as Training and Mentoring);-** 30.4% of the respondents insisted that; there should be incentives such as training, mentoring and flexibility in working hours, which will allow professional women who enter into the building construction industry, given the fact that; jobs in building construction sites are extremely labour intensive, and in most cases construction workers are often forced to deal with tight deadlines and high stress situations. Care must be taken when recruiting women as in some cases, a career in construction can cause a significant mental and physical strain on an individual, affecting their motivation. In order for construction projects to be completed, highly motivated and focused staffs are needed. Flexibility will allow workers to address other aspects of their lives hence balancing home and work commitments. More over simple gestures like monthly or weekly rewards are recommended as they can help boost morale and productivity, hence helping to retaining women in building construction industry.
- **Enhancement of Labour Laws and Regulations;-** 26.1% of the respondents revealed that; this can be achieved by ensuring that social dialogue takes place by involving key stakeholders such as the government, employers' and workers' organizations. The main goal

of social dialogue is to promote consensus building and democratic involvement among the main stakeholders in the world of building construction work. Under the UNDP, the ILO's work contributes in supporting the government achieve its human rights commitments, including rights of workers. In this respect, laws need to be reviewed to reflect national standards, that can accommodate more women in the building construction industry.

- **Supporting and Encouraging Women Participation in Building Construction;-** 17.4% of the respondents revealed that; hiring professional women from the beginning of the building construction industry, should be a priority, and they should be encouraged to participate in building construction regardless it is said to be a male-dominated sector. There should be development of new opportunities and recommendations to empower women in building construction industry, and the two aspects of strengthening women's participation should be mentoring and networking. This will also help to identify and evaluate existing mentoring programme for women in construction industry and establish a network of construction. Networking is also an important opportunity for strengthening women's participation, networks are considered to be an opportunity to build and increase social capital, increase understanding and knowledge, ease career transitions, establish collaborative work, develop personal connections, friendships and support each other regardless of location. As a result this will help to increase number of women participation in a construction industry.

Other recommendations revealed by the respondents includes; making recruitment of more women in building construction industry mandatory, which was revealed by 13.0% of the respondents; the need of employers to change their attitude, 4.3%; and promotion and increase on awareness which both had 8.7% of the respondents.

REFERENCES

- [1] Aboagye-Nimo, E., Wood, H., & Collison, J. (2019). Complexity of women's modernday challenges in construction. *Journal of Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1108/ECAM-09-2018-0421/>
- [2] Agapiou, A. (2002). Perceptions of gender roles and attitudes towards work among male and female operatives in the Scottish construction industry. *Journal of Construction Management and Economics*, 20(08), 697-705.
- [3] Ahuja, V. & Kumari, S. (2012). Issues and challenges for women in construction industry: Global as well as Indian perspective. In *Proceedings of the Regional Conference of the International Network of Women Engineers & Scientists (INWES), New Delhi, India*. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/264697438_Issues_and_challenges_for_women_in_construction_industry_Global_as_well_as_Indian_perspective.
- [4] Alves, S. & English, J. (2018). Female students' preparedness for a male-dominated workplace. *Journal of Engineering, Design and Technology*, 16(04), 581-595

- [5] Amaratunga, D., Haigh, R., Lee, A., & Elvitigala, E. (2009). Construction industry and women: A review of barriers. *International Journal of Construction Management and Economics*, 29(03), 559-571.
- [6] Aneke, E.O., Derera, E., & Bomani, M. (2017). An exploratory study of challenges faced by women entrepreneurs in the construction industry in South Africa. *International Journal of Business and Management Studies*, 09(02), 35-51.
- [7] Anuar, K.F., Abas, S.S.P., Ibrahim, A., & Hamzah, A.I.N. (2017). The barriers and challenges of women's involvement in the construction industry within Klang Valley area. *International Journal of Industrial Management (IJIM)*, 03, 61-75.
- [8] Aretoulis, G.N. (2018). Gender based perception of successful construction of project managers' attributes. *International Journal of Social Science*, 07(112). Available at: <http://www.mdpi.com/journal/socsci>.
- [9] Barg, J.E., Ruparathna, R., Mendis, D., & Hewage, K.N. (2014). Motivating workers in construction. *Journal of Construction Engineering*, Available at: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1155/2014/703084>.
- [10] Breugh, J.A. & Starke, M. (2000). Research on employee recruitment; so many studies, so many questions. *Journal of Management*, 26(03), 405-434.
- [11] Buncio, D.D. (2019). *The construction industry has a problem, and women are going to solve it*. Available at: <https://www.bdcnetwork.com/blog/construction-industry-has-problem-and-women-are-going-solve-it>.
- [12] Construction Industry Federation (CIF). (2019). *Women in the construction industry*. Available at: <https://cif.ie/wp-content/uploads/2018/03/CIF-Membership-Diversity-SURVEY-REPORT.pdf>.
- [13] Construction Industry Training Board (CITB). (2003). *Construction skills forecast report*. Available at: <http://www.citb.co.uk>.
- [14] Contractors Registration Board (CRB). (2015). *What is the way forward? Building capacity to local contractors*. Tanzania: CRB Newsletter.
- [15] Commonwealth Local Government Forum (CLGF). (2017). *The local government system in Tanzania: Country profile 2017-2018*. Available at: http://www.clgf.org.uk/default/assets/File/Country_profiles/Tanzania.pdf. Accessed on Friday, February 21, 2020.
- [16] English, J. & Hay, P. (2015). Black South African women in construction: cues for success. *Journal of Engineering, Design and Technology*, 13(01), 144-164.
- [17] English, J., Haupt T.C., & Smallwood, J.J. (2006). Women, construction and health and safety: South African and Tanzanian perspectives. *Journal of Engineering, Design and Technology*, 04(01), 18-28.
- [18] Fernando, N.G., Amaratunga, D., & Haigh, D. (2014). The career advancement of the professional women in the UK construction industry: The career success factors. *Journal of Engineering, Design and Technology (JEDT)*, 12(01), 53-70.
- [19] Fortune, J. (2010). I am the mother and the father—Women in construction in Cuba and the U.K. *International Journal of Cuban Studies*, 02(1/2), 147-156.
- [20] Francis, V. (2017). What influences professional women's career advancement in construction?. *Journal of Construction Management and Economics*, 35(05), 254-275.
- [21] French, E. & Strachan, S. (2015). Women at work! evaluating equal employment policies and outcomes in construction. *International Journal of Equality, Diversity and Inclusion*, 34(03), 227-243.
- [22] Galea, N., Powell, A., Loosemore, M., & Chappell, L. (2015). Designing robust and revisable policies for gender equality: Lessons from the Australian construction industry. *Journal of Construction Management and Economics*, 33(05/06), 375-389.
- [23] Gale, W.A. (1994). Women in non-traditional occupations: the construction industry. *Women in Management Review*, 09(02), 03-15.
- [24] Gurjao S. (2006). *Inclusivity: The changing role of women in the construction workforce*. CIOB.
- [25] Gyasi, A. (2012). *Assessing roles and contribution of women in the construction industry in Kumasi*. Unpublished MSc. Development Policy and Planning Dissertation, Kwame Nkrumah University of Science and Technology, Kumasi, Ghana, 104 Pages.
- [26] Hakala, S.R. (2008). *Women entrepreneurs: challenges and successes in non-traditional industries*. PhD Diss. University of Phoenix.
- [27] Hatipkarasulu, Y. & Roff, S.E. (2011). *Women in Construction: An Early Historical Perspective*. 47th ASC Annual International Conference Proceedings. Associated Schools of Construction.
- [28] English, J. & Hay, P. (2015). Black South African women in construction; cues for success. *Journal of Engineering, Design and Technology*, 13(01), 144-164.
- [29] Haupt, T. & Fester, F. (2012). Women-owned construction enterprises: a South African assessment. *Journal of Engineering, Design and Technology (JEDT)*, 10(01), 52-71.
- [30] Haupt, T. & Harinarain, N. (2016). The image of the construction industry and its employment attractiveness. *Acta Structilia*, 23(02), 79-108.
- [31] Higher Education Statistics Agency. (HESA). (2009). *All students by subject of study, domicile and gender*. Higher Education Statistics Agency.
- [32] International Labour Organization—(ILO). (2018). *World employment social outlook*. Switzerland: ILO Publication Bureau.
- [33] International Labour Organization—(ILO). (2015). *Good practices and challenges in promoting decent work in*

- construction and infrastructure projects*. An issues paper for discussion at the Global Dialogue Forum on Good Practices and Challenges in Promoting Decent Work in Construction and Infrastructure Projects, (Geneva, 19–20 November 2015), by Sectoral Policies Department, p-ISBN 978-92-2-130112-7; e-ISBN 978-92-2-130113-4, an ILO Publications Bureau, Geneva, Switzerland, 48 Pages.
- [34] International Labour Organization–(ILO). (2011). *Baseline study to assess gender disparities in construction sector jobs*. The Towards Gender Parity in Pakistan (TGP) Project. Islamabad, Pakistan: ILO Publications Bureau.
- [35] Jaafar, M. & Othman, N.L. (2013). Assessing the capability of women construction project managers based on liberal feminist theory. *International Journal of Construction Management*, 13(04), 35-52.
- [36] Jonas, S.N.M. (2015). *A model for the development of women in construction in the limpopo province of South Africa*. Unpublished Ph.D. Thesis in Rural Development, University of Venda, Thohoyandou, Limpopo Province, South Africa, 199 Pages.
- [37] Jongo, J.S., Tesha, D.N.G.A.K., Kassonga, R., Teyanga, J.J., & Lyimo, K.S. (2019). mitigation measures in dealing with delays and cost overrun in public building projects in Dar- Es-Salaam, Tanzania. *International Journal of Construction Engineering and Management (IJCEM)*, 08(3), 81-96.
- [38] Jongo, J.S., Tesha, D.N.G.A.K., Luvara., V.G.M., Teyanga, J.J., & Makule, E.T. (2018). fire safety preparedness in building construction sites in Dar-Es-Salaam, Tanzania. *International Journal of Engineering Trends and Technology (IJETT)*, 66(03), 154-169.
- [39] Kamugisha, A. (2012). *An analysis of the factors influencing the choice of careers in building industry by professional women in Tanzania*. Unpublished BSc. in Building Economics Dissertation, Department of Building Economics, ARDHI University(ARU), Dar-Es-Salaam, Tanzania.
- [40] Kalimullah A.R., Yaghoubi N.M., & Moloudi J. (2010). Survey of relationship between organizational justice and empowerment, (A case study). *European Journal of Economics, Finance and Administrative Sciences*, 24(03), 165-171.
- [41] Kihupi, D.J. (2012). *Challenges facing female workers working on construction sites in Tanzania*. Unpublished BSc. in Building Economics Dissertation, Department of Building Economics, ARDHI University(ARU), Dar-Es-Salaam, Tanzania.
- [42] Kikwasi, G.J. (2005). *Women in construction industry, the blocked resources*. The National Construction Council of Tanzania.
- [43] Kikwasi, G.J. (2005). *Increasing women employment in the construction industry*. Published PhD Thesis, Beijing University of Technology, Peoples Republic of China.
- [44] Kikwasi, G.J. & Escalante, C. (2018). *Roles of the construction sector and key bottlenecks to supply response in Tanzania*. The United Nations University (UNU) - World Institute for Development Economics Research (WIDER), WIDER Working Paper 2018/131, Published by UNU-WIDER, Helsinki, Finland, ISBN: 9789292565732, 24 Pages.
- [45] Kombo, D.K. & Tromp, D.L.A. (2014). *Proposal and thesis writing; An introduction*. (14th ed.). Nairobi, Kenya: Paulines Publication Africa.
- [46] Kothari, C.R. (2019). *Research methodology, methods and techniques*. (4th Revised ed.). Daryaganj, New Delhi: New Age International (Pvt) Limited Publishers.
- [47] Książek, M. & Kosy, K. (2017). *Gender aspects in construction*. Chapter 04, Page 67-103, In *Diversity Management in Construction*. 128 Pages, Construction Managers' Library, Erasmus+ 2015-1-PL01-KA202-016454, Published By Civil Engineering Faculty of Warsaw University of Technology, Warsaw, Poland, ISBN: 978-83-947920-3-9.
- [48] Kumar, R. (2011). *Research methodology: A step by step guide for beginners*. (3rd Revised ed.). New Delhi, India: SAGE Publication Pvt LTD.
- [49] Kumar, R.B. (2013). Gender discrimination among construction workers with reference to Vijayawada. *Journal of Sociology and Social Work*, 01(01), 42-53.
- [50] Kumar, K. & Chaturvedi, R. (2018). Women in construction industry: A work-life balance perspective. *International Journal of Civil Engineering and Technology (IJCIET)*, 09(08), 823-829.
- [51] Lema, N.M. (2017). *Human resource needs and skills development of the construction sector in Tanzania*. LTTP Report-Planning Commission, Unpublished Research Report.
- [52] Lombardi, M.R. (2017). *Women engineers in construction: the feminization possible and gender discrimination*. ISSUE IN FOCUS, São Paulo, Brasil, 24 Pages, (<http://dx.doi.org/10.1590/198053143619>).
- [53] Loosemore, M., Dainty, A., & Lingard, H. (2003). *Human resource management in construction projects: strategic and operational approaches*. London, United Kingdom: Spon Press, Published by Taylor & Francis.
- [54] Luvara, V.G.M. & Mwemezi, B.R. (2017). Obstacles against value management practice in building projects of Dar-Es-Salaam, Tanzania. *International Journal of Construction Engineering and Management (IJCEM)*, 06(01), 13-21.
- [55] Magigi, W. (2016). *Methodological tools for researching and scientific writing in emerging economies; A guide to understand research process, proposal writing, data collection, analysis and scientific writing*. Tanzania: Safi Publishers and Trading Co. LTD.
- [56] Malekela, K.N. & Daata, R.M. (2018). Assessment of gender issues in the construction industry in Tanzania.

International Journal of Engineering Trends and Technology (IJETT), 59(04), 175-181.

[57] Mathew, M. (2014). *Women in construction management: identification of the most effective factors in attracting and retaining freshmen and sophomore level students*. Unpublished Dissertation for a Master of Science Degree in Construction Management, Graduate and Professional Studies, Texas A&M University, 109 Pages.

[58] Mikapagaro, N.A., Tesha, D.N.G.A.K., Maro, G.C., & Edson, B.K. (2018). The implementation of risk management strategies in joint venture building projects in Dar-Es-Salaam, Tanzania. *International Journal of Engineering Trends and Technology (IJETT)*, 66(03), 133-153.

[59] Moir, S. Thomson, M., & Kelleher, C. (2011). *Unfinished business:- Building equality for women in the construction trades*. A Research Report from the Labor Resource Center, College of Public and Community Service, and the Center for Women in Politics & Public Policy, McCormack Graduate School of Policy and Global Studies, Published by Labor Resource Center Publications. Paper #05, Page 37. Available at: http://scholarworks.umb.edu/lrc_pubs/5.

[60] Msangi, N. (2018). *Assessment of motivation and challenges facing women quantity surveyors in consulting firms*. BSc. in Building Economics Dissertation, Department of Building Economics, ARDHI University (ARU), Dar-Es-Salaam, Tanzania.

[61] Naismith, N., Robertson, S., & Tookey, J. (2017). Identifying barriers to retaining female professionals in engineering and construction organizations. *EPiC Series in Education Science Journal, AUBEA 2017: Australasian Universities Building Education Association Conference*, 01, 227-234.

[62] National Women's Law Center (NWLC). (2014). *Women in construction still breaking ground*. Available at: https://www.nwlc.org/sites/default/files/pdfs/final_nwlc_womeninconstruction_report.pdf.

[63] Navarro-Astor, E., Román-Onsalo, M., & Infante-Perea, M. (2017). Women's career development in the construction industry across 15 years: main barriers. *Journal of Engineering, Design and Technology*, 15(02), 199-221.

[64] Nayak, J.K. & Singh, P. (2015). *Fundamentals of research methodology: Problems and prospects*. (1st ed.). New Delhi, India: SSDN Publisher & Distributors.

[65] Ngonde, D.F. (2015). *Job satisfaction among workers in the construction industry: A case of national housing corporation*. Unpublished Dissertation Submitted for the Degree of Master of Business Administration of the Open University of Tanzania, 80 Pages.

[66] National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). (2016). *Tanzania construction*. Available at: www.tanzaniainvest.com

[67] NBS. (2014). *Integrated labour force survey*. United Republic of Tanzania.

[68] Okangi, F.P. (2018). Linking entrepreneurial motivation factors to firm growth:- Empirical evidence from the construction industry in Tanzania. *Journal of Business Management Review*, 21(02), 30-42.

[69] Othman, N.L. & Jaafar, M. (2013). Personal competency of selected women construction project managers in Malaysia. *Journal of Engineering, Design and Technology*, 11(03), 276-287.

[70] Osubor, O. (2016). Factors that influence female folks to engage in building and civil engineering construction site work in Nigeria- A case study of Isoko women. *American Journal of Engineering Research (AJER)*, 05(11), 131-137.

[71] Pruzan, P.M. (2016). *Research methodology: The aims, practices and ethics of science*. Switzerland: Springer International.

[72] Rajanna, K.A. (2015). Nature of work, working conditions and problems of women construction workers: A case study. *International Journal of Business Quantitative Economics and Applied Management Research*, 01(09), 70-85.

[73] Regis, M.F., Alberte, E.P.V., Lima, D.D., & Freitas, R.L.S. (2019). Women in construction: shortcomings, difficulties, and good practices. *Journal of Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*. Available at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/ECAM-09-2018-0425>.

[74] Rosa, J.E., Hon, C.K.H., Xia, B., & Lamari, F. (2017). Challenges, success factors and strategies for women's career development in the Australian construction industry. *International Journal of Construction Economics and Building*, 17(03), 27-46.

[75] Rusetski, A. (2011). Getting proactive: Cultural and procedural drivers of managerial motivation to act. *Journal of Business & Economic Research*, 09(01). Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/293022632_Getting_Proactive_Cultural_And_Procedural_Drivers_Of_Manual_Motivation_To_Act/download.

[76] Samwel, J.O. (2018). An assessment of the challenges facing recruitment, selection and retention process in small industries in Mwanza region. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention (IJBMI)*, 07(03), 35-41.

[77] Sangweni, N. (2015). *Women in construction: hindrances that shorten the professional working life of female site engineers on construction sites in South Africa*. Unpublished Master of Science in Building (Project Management in Construction), Research Report, Faculty of Engineering & Built Environment, University of the Witwatersrand, Johannesburg, South Africa, 121 Pages.

[78] Sang, K.J.C. & Powell, A. (2012). *Equality, diversity, inclusion and work life balance in construction*. (2nd ed.). 34 Pages, in a Dainty, A., & Loosemore, M., (Eds.), *Human Resource Management in Construction: Critical*

- Perspectives*", (2nd Edition., Page 163 to 196). Routledge. (<https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203842478>).
- [79] Saris, W.E. & Gallhofer, I.N. (2014). *Design, evaluation, and analysis of questionnaires for survey research*. (2nd ed.). Canada: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- [80] Scott, J., Dex, S., Joshi, H. (2008). *Women and employment; changing lives and new challenges*. Cheltenham, Northampton, USA: Edward Elgar Publishing Limited.
- [81] Shadare, O.A. & Hamed, T.A. (2009). Influence of work motivation, leadership effectiveness and time management on employees' performance in some elected industries in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Economics, Finance and Administrative Sciences*, 01(06), 07-17.
- [82] Sospeter, G.N. (2016). Model for exploring women entrepreneurial motivation in the Tanzanian construction industry. *Journal of Business Management Review*, 19(01). Available at: https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/6b1d/79e7badd6063e844a89d59df075b86f1cff1.pdf?_ga=2.93631518.2096603751.1582122467-339894083.1545142831.
- [83] Sospeter, G.N. (2016). Challenges facing women entrepreneurs in the construction industry in Tanzania. *Journal of Business and Economics*, 07(11), 1907-1918.
- [84] Sospeter, G.N., Rwelamila, P.D., Nchimbi., & Masoud, M. (2014). Review of theory and practice literature on women entrepreneurship in the Tanzanian construction industry: Establishing the missing link. *Journal of Construction in Developing Countries (JCDC)*, 19(02), 75-85.
- [85] Tessa, W. (2016). *Gender and sexuality in male-dominated occupations, women working in construction and transport*. London, United Kingdom: Springer Nature.
- [86] United Republic of Tanzania-(URT). (2016). *The national five year development plan 2016/17 – 2020/21;- Nurturing industrialization for economic transformation and human development*. Ministry of Finance and Planning, Published by Government Printers, Dodoma, Tanzania, 316 Pages.
- [87] United Republic of Tanzania-(URT). (2018). *The economic survey 2017*. Dodoma, Tanzania: Ministry of Finance and Planning, Government Printers.
- [88] Watts, J.H. (2009). *Leaders of men: Women managing in construction*. *Journal of Work, Employment and Society*, 23(03), 512-530.
- [89] Whiteley, P. (2002). *Motivation*. Oxford, United Kingdom: Capstone Publishing.
- [90] Wright, T. (2014). *The women into construction project: An assessment of a model for increasing women's participation in construction*. Centre for Research in Equality and Diversity,(CRED), School of Business and Management, Queen Mary University of London, London, United Kingdom (U.K.), 72 Pages.
- [91] Zinyemba, A.Z. (2014). *The challenges of recruitment and selection of employees in Zimbabwean companies*. *International Journal of Science and Research*, 03(01), 29-33.